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Synthesis of The Report: Drivers and Barriers of Civic Engagement in Open Science and The Role of University Libraries in The Baltics

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This article presents a synthesis of the report “Drivers and Barriers of Civic Engagement in Open Science and The Role of University Libraries in The Baltics” for the project “University libraries strengthening the academia-society connection through citizen science in the Baltics” under the Erasmus+ Programme, Key Action 2: Partnerships for Cooperation. The full report is available to read in English in the project [Zenodo collection](#).

Citizen science in connection to Open Science and academic libraries

University libraries in the Baltics play a crucial role in fostering Open Science within their organisations. They have experience in participating in different initiatives and working groups, being involved in policy-making but also supporting researchers, students and the teaching staff with advising and building skills related to Open Science practices.

Research libraries also provide their infrastructure to the general public. Given that they are open to the public and not restricted to their staff and students, they provide a significant opportunity for civic engagement and linking to society. Citizen science has the potential to bring forth many scientific and societal opportunities for Europe. It also offers opportunities for learning about new topics and personal growth. Yet, the number and impact of such activities remain low and integrating civic engagement into the Open Science cycle is still at its initial stage.

Oxford English Dictionary defines citizen science as “scientific work undertaken by members of the general public, often in collaboration with or under the direction of professional scientists

and scientific institutions” (Oxford English Dictionary, n.d). However, a wide variety of terms and expressions are used to describe the context of citizen science. Eitzel and colleagues (2017) explored the term in a broad sense and included activities such as generating any theory or hypothesis, research, scientific data collection, and/or data analysis, in which the public is involved.

Although the term “citizen science” is relatively new, the public has engaged in science for as long as it has existed. Europe has a large community of citizen scientists. There is, however, a large imbalance in the development of citizen science projects among different countries in Europe. Countries such as the UK, Germany, Switzerland, and others in Western Europe have a much better-developed infrastructure for implementing citizen science projects than countries in Central and Eastern Europe such as Latvia, Lithuania, and Estonia (Vohland et al., 2021).

Citizen science is recognized as one of the eight ambitions of the European Commission’s definition of Open Science. They state that “The general public should be able to make significant contributions and be recognised as valid European science knowledge producers.” (European Commission, 2019). The mission of Open Science is to make scientific research, data and dissemination accessible at all levels (Ayrís & Ignat, 2018). One aspect of it is producing and sharing knowledge in open and collaborative ways (European Commission, 2019).

Research libraries are therefore in an excellent position to foster Open Science activities, including participating in citizen science projects. The Association of European Research Libraries (LIBER) proposed in their Open Science Roadmap (Ayrís et al., 2018) the specific actions libraries can take to promote Open Science activities. They also focused specifically on citizen science.

The Roadmap notes that research libraries should be actively promoted as partners in citizen science projects and build an infrastructure that enables them to support citizen scientists (Ayrís et al., 2018: 28). In addition, they should develop a set of guidelines for libraries which outline their activity in civic engagement. They recommend building specific skills that allow libraries to be strong partners, especially concerning scientific communication, information technologies and project management. Furthermore, libraries should make sure that citizen science projects follow responsible conduct and good scholarly practice. (Ayrís et al., 2018: 28).

The current report aimed to identify the drivers and barriers of civic engagement in open science and the role of university libraries in the Baltics. To consider all perspectives, three separate roundtables were held for a) researchers and teaching staff (n=19), b) librarians (n=23) and c) university students (n=20) of Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania. The three perspectives demonstrate variance in opinions and help address them on an institutional level.

The study was carried out in March of 2022. All roundtables were recorded, transcribed and later analysed with a six-step thematic analysis. The authors proposed three research questions:

1. What are the current drivers that could enable academic libraries to participate in citizen science projects?
2. What are the current barriers that have not enabled academic libraries to participate in citizen science projects?
3. How to further develop collaboration between academic libraries and civic engagement?

As previous studies have not focused on the opinions of researchers, librarians and higher education students on the drivers and barriers of civic engagement in research libraries in the Baltics, this study fills that gap.

Results of the study

The study revealed that research librarians already have many skills that could be useful for participating in citizen science projects. The most value was seen in their research data management, communication and digital literacy skills. All three are important for the success of citizen science projects. Mačiulienė & Butkevičienė (2022) found communication to be essential for citizen science projects, and this includes both outward and inward communication. The library can act as a liaison between participants, scientists and the media. As university libraries have already established national and international networks, experience in disseminating information about their events, and a strong connection and motivation to move towards a society where science is open for all, they could use their channels to disseminate information regarding different projects.

In addition to dissemination, the participants suggested that librarians could train citizen scientists in research data management and digital literacy. The participants included information and scientific literacy under the latter category. Teaching citizen scientists about

scientific literacy were also touched upon in the LIBER's guide "Citizen Science Skilling for Library Staff, Researchers, and the Public" (2021). Furthermore, libraries could ensure that citizen science projects follow good scholarly and ethical practices. (Ayris et al., 2018).

The study also revealed that the infrastructure in research libraries could benefit citizen science projects. Libraries could make their rooms, repositories and servers available to citizen scientists. This was also proposed by Ayris and Ignat (2018: 18-19) in their recommendations for libraries to get involved in citizen science projects. All three stakeholder groups saw the library as a physical meeting space. As they are by nature open to the public without any restrictions, libraries could offer their rooms for meetings and training. This way, the library could become an intellectual hub as was proposed in the LIBER guide (Kaarsted & Worthington, 2021).

Researchers thought that the library should be responsible for citizen science data. First, the library could offer their institutional repositories to keep the data, perform quality control and publish it in accordance with the FAIR principles. Second, they could provide citizen scientists with training regarding open data skills.

Interestingly, students were unaware of the different services the library provides and therefore had difficulty identifying which resources could be helpful to citizen scientists. This showed that there is a stereotype of libraries being only study spaces and for scientific literature, instead of multifunctional science support centres, in the respondents' perception. Researchers suggested that changing the stereotype would bring more opportunities for collaboration to research libraries.

The main limitation of research libraries' participation in civic engagement was the lack of knowledge of citizen science. Both librarians and university students noted that they know too little about citizen science, different projects and how they could be involved. This was reflected in the lack of cooperation between the librarians and researchers who participated in the study as they commented that the library should take more initiative. Therefore, it can be presumed that the lack of collaborative projects is not due to little interest but little knowledge.

Another limitation was the lack of support from universities. There are a few aspects to it. First, as research libraries operate under their universities, their finances and assignments depend on the universities' strategy. If citizen science is not a priority for them, research libraries lack the resources to be more actively involved. This confirms findings from previous studies that

citizen science projects in the Baltics need more systemic institutional support (Suškevičs et al., 2021; Mačiulienė & Butkevičienė, 2022). This includes universities but also policymakers who allocate funds for higher education institutes.

The second aspect of it is the lack of specialists. Even though academic libraries could help with research data management, curation, and collection, there are not enough specialists who could offer support to citizen scientists in addition to their regular assignments. Many libraries have a data steward but if there is only one person per organisation, they simply do not have time to deal with citizen science projects next to helping researchers and students. Participants thought that if citizen science becomes more of a priority for universities, there would be more resources to hire more specialists.

The third aspect deals with teaching about citizen science activities in universities. Almost all students who participated in the study had not learnt about the topic at the university. If some had been involved in any citizen science projects, it had not been a part of their curriculum or any requirements from class. Ayriss and Ignat (2018) proposed that libraries could develop a training programme which teaches undergraduates about citizen science. This would help strengthen the collaboration between the university and the library, and also teach students the necessary skills for participating in citizen science. Teaching undergraduates will also have the benefit of new potential citizen scientists.

All participant groups mentioned the need for a platform which unites both general information about citizen science and different ongoing projects as there currently is no such national platform in Baltic countries except for Lithuania. This was something that the participants of the study imagined a research library could take on. While they are already supporting people on scientific literacy, if the library could provide information and resources necessary to participate in citizen science projects, the role of a citizen science hub could be achieved.

Guidelines for research libraries

Based on the analysis of the interviews and literature, the authors developed guidelines which could be useful for future projects and collaboration:

1. Train the staff of research libraries on data collection, management, and curation.
2. Establish new positions in research libraries focused on civic engagement.

3. Appoint a liaison person at the research library who is responsible for uniting citizen scientists with the university faculty.
4. Stress the need for stronger support from the universities.
5. Establish a central platform which unites information about how to participate, which skills are needed and which projects are looking for volunteers.

Concluding remarks

The overall study has some limitations. As the participants in this study had varied experiences and the working language was English, valuable input might have been missed due to the lack of language skills and limited knowledge of citizen science in the Baltics context. Comparing the study results with the theory gives valuable input, however, it needs to be considered that it reflects the opinions of stakeholders and has not been tested in practice by the authors of this study as of yet.

Citizen science as part of Open Science can take a number of forms, from simply being informed about scientific research to actively becoming involved with the research process. Citizens can help address the pan-European Open Science effort to open, share and re-use research to solve various societal problems. Thus, citizen science has a real potential for Open Science. By exploring the drivers and barriers of civic engagement in university libraries we are one step closer to moving to the next stage with the implementation of civic engagement in the Baltics.

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